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KADA POČINJE LJUDSKI ŽIVOT? PRILOG RASPRAVI O PRAVNOJ ZAŠTITI NEROĐENOG DETETA

U fokusu našeg rada nalazi se jedno veoma važno, složeno i teško pitanje – kada počinje ljudski život. To pitanje je od velikog značaja i za pravnu nauku, mada ona nije u stanju da ponudi odgovor na njega, oslanjajući se na svoju juridičku aparaturu. Predmet pravne nauke nije čovek kao biološko ili psihološko biće već isključivo kao pravni subjekt sa određenim fondom subjektivnih prava i obaveza. Iako pravnici nisu kompetentni da utvrđuju kada počinje ljudski život, oni su pozvani da opredeljuju vrstu, obim, stepen i početak pravne zaštite ljudskog života. Smatramo da se ne može na zadovoljavajući način odgovoriti na ovo poslednje pitanje, ako ne postoji spremnost pravne nauke da izađe iz okova sopstvene samoograničenosti i pokaže interesovanje i za one oblasti koje su referentne za davanje odgovora na prvo pitanje. Tu, pre svega, spadaju neke prirodne nauke, kao što su biologija, medicina i genetika, a u poslednje vreme i jedna mlada društvena nauka – prenatalna psihologija. Naš prevashodni istraživački zadatak u ovom radu biće upravo pretresanje naučnih dostignuća s tim u vezi u navedenim oblastima. Međutim, neko ko je homo religiosus (a Jung bi rekao da svi mi nosimo u sebi taj arhetip), oseća potrebu da odgovor na prvo pitanje potraži i u religiji. Teološki aspekt sagledaćemo kroz prizmu monoteističkih religija, s posebnim osvrtom na pravoslavno učenje. Naš zadatak se komplikuje ukoliko se pokaže da navedene naučne oblasti početak ljudskog života ne određuju na jedinstven način. Dodatni problem predstavljaće eventualni raskorak u tom pogledu između nauke i religije. Zato bi naš sledeći korak bio pokušaj iznalaženja načelnog odgovora na pitanje koga to onda treba da slušaju pravnici prilikom obavljanja svog dela posla i da li prilikom osmišljavanja pravne zaštite nerođenog deteta mogu da budu arbiterni.

Ključne reči: početak ljudskog života, nerođeno dete, medicina, prenatalna psihologija, hrišćanstvo, pravo.

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WHEN DOES HUMAN LIFE BEGIN? A CONTRIBUTION TO THE DISCUSSION ON THE LEGAL PROTECTION OF THE UNBORN CHILD

The focal point in this paper is a very important, complex, and difficult question: when does human life begin? This question is of great significance for legal science, but law cannot providing an answer to this question by relying solely on its juridical apparatus. The subject matter of legal science is not the human being as a biological or psychological entity, but exclusively as a legal subject having a certain set of subjective rights and obligations. Although legal scholars are not competent to determine when human life begins, they are called upon to define the type, scope, degree, and the starting point of the legal protection of human life. We believe that the last issue cannot be addressed in a satisfactory manner unless legal science is willing to step beyond the confines of its self-imposed limitations and show interest in those areas that are relevant to answering the first question. These areas include certain natural sciences, such as biology, medicine, and genetics, and, more recently, prenatal psychology as a young social science. The primary research task in this paper will be to examine the scientific findings in these areas. However, someone who is homo religiosus (and Jung noted that we all carry that archetype within us) feels the need to seek the answer to the first question in religion. The theological aspect will be considered through the prism of monotheistic religions, with special reference to the Orthodox Christianity teaching. The research task becomes more complex if it turns out that the aforesaid scientific disciplines do not define the beginning of human life in a uniform way. In this regard, an additional problem may arise from a possible discrepancy between science and religion. Therefore, the next step will be an attempt to find a general answer to the question concerning who legal professionals should listen to when performing their part of the work, and whether they may act arbitrarily in shaping the legal protection of the unborn child.

Keywords: beginning of human life, unborn child, medicine, prenatal psychology, Christianity, law.